

A glycotherapeutic approach to functionalize biomaterials-based systems

Anuja Gadekar[#], Sirsendu Bhowmick^{#*} and Abhay Pandit^{*}

***Corresponding Authors:** Prof. Abhay Pandit & Dr. Sirsendu Bhowmick, SFI Research Centre for Medical Devices (CÚRAM), Biomedical Sciences, National University of Ireland Galway, Ireland.

Email: abhay.pandit@nuigalway.ie, sirsendu.bhowmick@nuigalway.ie

[#]These authors have contributed equally to this work.

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Abstract:

In addition to being one of the primary building block materials of living cells, glycans also have a potential as the favorable candidates for therapeutic applications. In the mid-20th century, the progress of glycans in the drug discovery field became surpassed by protein and DNA-focused treatments. However, the emergence of new analytical tools and methods to synthesize structurally specific glycans has encouraged and motivated the scientific community towards the development of glycan-based therapeutics. This review discusses the reemergence of glycan-based agents in the last decade and the technical strategies that played a key role in bringing the glycan-based treatments into the limelight of modern medicine. The review also includes the application of native glycans as the therapeutic agents along with the chemically engineered cell surface glycans and proteins to meet the preclinical and clinical scenario. Glycan-based therapeutic materials hold a huge potential that can be harnessed to meet the clinical needs in medicine.

26 **Introduction:**

27 Glycans are integral and basic modules of life and are observed in various forms in nature
28 such as secreted mucus components of varying chain lengths from monosaccharide to long
29 polysaccharides and large polysaccharides ^[1]. These carbohydrate moieties are the most
30 abundant class of organic moieties in the world and can be found on the cellular surface of
31 every organism^[2]. The molecular structure of monosaccharides was explained for the first
32 time in the mid-1880s by Fischer. However, it was almost a century after Fisher's discovery;
33 before experts started to realize the crucial parts of these moieties modulating the biological
34 phenomenon ^[3]. This delay in exploring the functionality of glycans was mainly because of the
35 complexity associated with the assembly and regulation of these biomacromolecules. Cellular
36 processes such as metabolism and signal transduction govern the biosynthesis and
37 functionality of glycans, as they are not openly encoded by the genome ^[4]. Moreover, glycans
38 can be attached to a group of stereochemistry and regiochemistry-based linkages. This could
39 lead to a wide range of structural diversity which can be further explained via the
40 modifications found in the present functional group^[5].

41 It is widely reported that glycans play a crucial part in numerous biophysical phenomena such
42 as cellular adhesion, proliferation, migration, differentiation, organism development,
43 immune response modulation and disease progression ^[6]. In spite of extensive research and
44 several reports on the influence of glycans on the disease, medical chemists and clinicians
45 hardly recognized the glycan molecules as a potent target moieties or drugs^[7]. The prime
46 research interests of sugar in biology were in general limited to its role as a source of energy
47 for a long time. This unawareness is starting to fade away as advanced methodology regarding
48 sugar synthesis^[8], sequencing^[9] and biological evaluation^[10] became more refined and easily
49 accessible. Over the last few decades, researchers have been studying glycans, either bound
50 to proteins or in lipids (Figure 1) and have become aware of their essential roles in different
51 biological activities such as cell-cell recognition^[11], cell signaling^[12], cellular differentiation^[13]
52 and immune response^[14]. This diverse functional ability of carbohydrates is now being
53 exploited for the use of carbohydrates in therapeutic approaches.

54 To gain a better understanding of glycans and the emerging glycotherapy, in this review we
55 have summarized a detailed history of the emergence of glycans as therapeutics. To achieve
56 high targetability of drug molecules, glycan-based delivery systems are often used to exploit

57 the interaction between glycans and lectin receptors. Thus, the knowledge of different lectin
58 receptors and their location in our body is of vital importance for the design of
59 glycotherapeutics. We have provided here a brief overview of a variety of lectin receptors
60 present in our body, the cells/tissues they are expressed on and the glycans that can be
61 recognized by them. Along with this, information about different glycosylation strategies that
62 can be employed to achieve the desired glycoconjugation of the materials in focus mentioned
63 in this review will help researchers for the design of glycotherapeutics for the desired
64 targeting application. Lastly, we have provided a detailed summary of glycotherapeutics that
65 have been designed in the last couple of decades for various delivery applications and as drug
66 molecules. This review emphasizes and reevaluates various approaches available to engineer
67 glycan's for biomedical application by closely analyzing the recent advances in the area of
68 glyco-chemical biology and carbohydrate chemistry. Using available carbohydrate research
69 tools, researchers are developing advanced glycan-based materials to improve human
70 wellbeing and treat illness. The field of glycoengineering is considered relatively undeveloped
71 by the scientific community, yet this largely uncharted area holds unlimited potential towards
72 the development of new generation therapeutics.

73

74 Figure 1: Cell surface glycans in mammals. The diagram depicts different types of glyco-
 75 protein and glyco-lipid linkages present on the exterior of the cell. Glycans can be bound to
 76 proteins as glycoproteins or proteoglycans. N- and O- linked glycans are very common in
 77 mammals. Glucosphingolipids (GSLs) are the major glycolipids in mammals found in the cell
 78 membrane of the organisms. Sugar symbols are according to the symbol nomenclature for
 79 glycans. Abbreviations in the key: GlcNAc, N-acetylglucosamine; GalNAc, N-
 80 acetylgalactosamine; Gal, galactose; Glc, glucose; Man, mannose; Fuc, fucose; Sia, sialic acid;
 81 Xyl, xylose; GlcA, glucuronic acid; IdoA, iduronic acid.

82 **The historical background of the therapeutic application of glycans**

83 Glycans have had a very profuse past in therapeutic applications similar to other biomolecules
 84 such as nucleic acid and protein. Yet due to the evolution of DNA technologies and the
 85 discovery of the genetic code, lipids and glycans became a less valued candidate for biological
 86 target or drug as protein and DNA are considered as two main components of life. However,
 87 this relatively short period of oversight has not reduced the significance of glycans for
 88 medicinal usage ^[15]. The increase in type II diabetes and obesity was a vivid example of the

89 biological role of glycans and lipids in understanding and the treatment of the burgeoning
90 epidemic^[16].

91 Karl Landsteiner revealed the different blood groups (A, B and O) in 1900 and he was
92 presented with Nobel Prize in Medicine in 1930. This discovery allowed clinicians to match
93 blood donors to and perform the first successful blood transfusion in 1907. However, for the
94 next 50 years, the ABO constituents' structures were not explored. Several research groups
95 have tried to identify the structure of ABO constituents but they were not successful until the
96 discovery of the following: (a) plant lectins that attached with blood group-specific cells and
97 (b) ovarian cyst, a source of abundant active compound that was discovered in the 1950s^[17].
98 Kabat et al. found that the fucose, a monosaccharide which attached with galactose (Gal) and
99 *N*-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) to create B and A antigen, was the key component of H
100 antigen, respectively^[17-18]. In the 1960s, the complete structure was discovered by the
101 ingenious application of a selective alkylation process associated with acid/base and
102 enzymatic hydrolysis for defining the components and monosaccharide linkages^[17].

103 In 1916, McLean discovered heparin, a polysaccharide and with progress in the method of
104 isolation from animals; it was being used clinically by the 1930s^[19]. These advances in
105 heparin's application for therapeutic purposes made a strong impact on the medical and
106 clinical community. Up until the 1950s, the main source of commercial heparin was porcine
107 mucosa. At that time, the industrial production of heparin was around 100 tons/year and it
108 was solely dependent on extraction from an animal source. The researchers who were trying
109 to investigate the molecular mechanism of heparin fueled the discovery of antithrombin III,
110 which plays a crucial role as an inhibitor of the enzymatic activity of thrombin^[20]. Before 1980,
111 the chemical structure of heparin's disaccharide unit was not revealed and afterward, Lindahl
112 et al. reported that it comprises sulfated glucosamine and iduronic acid, underlining the
113 linkage of heparin to the glycosaminoglycan (GAG) family^[20b]. Fascinatingly, in a human mast
114 cell subset, the endogenous heparin was observed where it was acting as a controller for the
115 elements of granules that were used for immune protection purposes^[21]. These findings, as
116 well as the clinical application, have converted heparin into a billion-dollar industry.

117 It was observed by Avery and Dochez that a "soluble-specific substance" isolated
118 from *Pneumococcus* was interacting with antisera (type-specific) isolated from diseased
119 individuals^[22]. Afterward, Avery collaborated with Heidelberger, a pioneer in the antibody

120 domain, and found that the “soluble-specific substance” is actually a polysaccharide-based
121 type-specific soluble material^[23]. The findings of Avery and Heidelberger were not fully
122 recognized by the scientific community up until 1930 when Francis and Tillett reported that
123 this respective glycan acts as a major element in vaccine preparation towards
124 *Pneumococcus*^[24]. Historically, these capsular polysaccharide-based therapeutic products
125 were used for various clinical needs. Twenty-three purified capsular polysaccharides isolated
126 from *Streptococcus pneumoniae* were used to develop the vaccine Pneumovax (PPV23)^[25],
127 whereas a few amounts of capsular polysaccharide isolated from other microbes were able
128 to generate enough IgG/IgM mediated immune response during vaccination. These findings
129 became a milestone and motivated several research groups to explore the other potent
130 sugars for vaccine development.

131 Aminoglycosides are well-known small molecule glycans, produced by some specific gram-
132 positive bacteria's such as the *Micromonospora* and *Streptomyces* genus. Streptomycin, the
133 first aminoglycoside, was discovered in 1943. It was the first antibiotic that effectively cured
134 tuberculosis and found pragmatic clinical application^[26]. Kanamycin, neomycin, and
135 gentamycin are widely used antibiotics which also belong to the same antibiotic family.
136 Aminoglycosides act as inhibitors for protein synthesis; however, the exact mode of action
137 for all the aminoglycosides is not yet fully explored^[27]. Unfortunately, the clinical application
138 for aminoglycosides has decreased due to the rapid onset of bacterial resistance, but then
139 again, the increase in multidrug-resistant bacterial strains has re-motivated the scientific
140 community to engineer new drugs or a target compounds to block the multidrug-resistant
141 bacterial strains^[10].

142 Positron emission tomography (PET) which revolutionized the field of clinical oncology was
143 first developed around the 1950s. It was the discovery of the chemical synthesis procedure of
144 2-fluorodeoxy-deoxy-glucose (FDG) and its application in bioimaging that fueled the invention
145 of PET 20 years later^[28]. Cells with a higher metabolic rate usually take ¹⁸FDG more quickly
146 than other cells with less metabolic demand and this led to the imaging of brain cells as well
147 as to the detection of tumors^[29]. Alternative direct imaging techniques for glycans and other
148 biomacromolecules took several more decades to appear and this has been discussed briefly
149 but not elaborated further in this review^[10, 30].

Figure 2: Timeline with the key milestones in the historical development of glycans in medicine. The beginning of the 20th century encompasses major breakthroughs in medicine with glycan-based therapies. However, later progress in the clinical developments of glycan-based therapeutics was hindered by the lack of structural understanding. In the later 20th century and early 21st century, the development of new techniques and the key findings of the specific glycan structure activity resulted in the emergence of a research field called glycobiology.

150 **Importance of lectin receptors in glycotherapy**

151 The cell surface receptors that can bind with the carbohydrates are known as the membrane
152 lectins. Various carbohydrates can be used as the ligands for these lectin membrane receptors
153 to target therapeutic agents ^[31]. The lectin's interaction with the glycosylated composite
154 could be evaluated by studying the binding of glycosylated materials with lectins viz.,
155 concanavalin A (Con A) and Ricinus communis agglutinin ^[32]. The interaction between
156 endogenous ligands and different carbohydrates such as lactose, mannose, fructose,
157 galactose, and fucose can be used to target sugar ligands ^[33]. It has been widely reported that
158 the glycosylated drug carrier i.e. a drug carrier conjugated with sugar moieties as surface
159 ligands can be recognized and later endocytosed by lectin receptors. LecB, a fucose specific
160 lectin is usually linked to tissue attachment as well as to biofilm construction due to microbial
161 contamination specifically from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Kolomiets et al. have designed a
162 glycopeptides dendrimer-based system using dendrimers of C-fucosyl peptide for preparing
163 LecB inhibitor as an antimicrobial agent ^[34]. Enzyme-linked lectin assay (ELLA) showed a strong
164 affinity of these fucose-terminal-glycopeptides dendrimers towards lectin. Octavalent and
165 Tetravalent ligand showed significantly higher binding affinity than fucose. The concept of the
166 uptake of a glycosylated carrier via a lectin receptor has been investigated thoroughly for
167 screening different molecules that have therapeutic potential. Likewise, it was observed that
168 C-fucosyl conjugated glycopeptide dendrimers selectively bind with *Ulex europaeus* lectin.
169 The modified dendrimers also showed a higher binding affinity for PA-IIL lectin derived from
170 *P. aeruginosa* ^[35].

Table:1 A summary of lectin receptors

Types of lectin receptor	Glycans	Expressed on	Tissue/Organ	Ligand	Targets	Ref
Mannose receptor (lectin receptor C-type)	α-Man	Kuffer and endothelial cells (Non-parenchymal origin)	Liver	Glycoproteins with mannose moieties	Receptor driven rapid endocytosis	[36]
		Macrophages	Lungs, liver, spleen, bone marrow and brain	Glycoproteins with mannose residue	Macrophage internalization	[37]
		Dendritic cells	Blood, lymph node and spleen	Complex protein terminal with mannose residue	Delivery of targeted nucleic acid for pathogen recognition (vaccination)	[37b, 38]
Asialoglycoprotein receptors	β-Gal	Hepatic-parenchymal cells	Liver	Galactosyl residues	Therapeutic agent targeting to liver cells	[39]
Galactosyl receptor	β-Gal	Kupffer and liver endothelial cells	Liver	Compound with galactose moieties	Sulfated glycoprotein removal from blood	[40]
Fucose receptors DG-SIGN	α-Fuc	Kupffer cells	Liver	Compound with fucose moieties	Targeted therapeutic agent delivery to Kupffer cells	[41]
Fucose receptor	α-Fuc, α-Man	Conjunctival and corneal cells	Eye	N-acetyl-D-galactosamine and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine	Delivery of therapeutic molecules to ocular space	[42]
		Buccal cells, oral epithelium	Oral cavity	Significant lectin affinity, specially lectins originating from Arachis hypogaea and Pisum sativum	Delivery of selected therapeutic agent to Buccal cavity	[43]
DC-SIGN	Lewis x Gal-β1-4GlcNAc Fucα1-3	Malignant tumor cells	Tumor/Cancerous tissue	Sugars like mannose, lactose, galactose, fucose, SiaLe-X	Targeted delivery of antineoplastic agents into malignant tumor tissue	[33b, 44]
	Lewis y Fucα1-2Gal-β1-4GlcNAc Fucα1-3	Malignant tumor cells	Tumor/Cancerous tissue	Sugars like mannose, lactose, galactose, fucose, SiaLe-Y	Targeted delivery of antineoplastic agents into malignant tumor tissue	[45]
SIGN-R1 DC-SIGN	Lewis a Galβ1-3GlcNAc Fucα1-4	Malignant tumor cells	Tumor/Cancerous tissue	Sugars like mannose, lactose, galactose, fucose, SiaLe-A	Targeted delivery of antineoplastic agents into malignant tumor tissue	[46]
	H type Fucα1-2Gal-β1-3GlcNAc	Malignant tumor cells	Tumor/Cancerous tissue		Targeted delivery of antineoplastic agents into malignant tumor tissue	[47]

171 Table 1 shows a summary of lectin receptors expressed by a variety of cells. It is well known
172 that a variety of receptors for sugar molecules are expressed in liver cells. Hepatocytes, the
173 liver parenchymal cells can detect a galactose molecule or compound having residues of
174 galactosyl using the asialoglycoprotein transmembrane receptors; whereas the non-
175 parenchymal cells viz., (a) liver endothelial and (b) Kupffer cells possess a mannose receptor
176 [36, 39a, 39b, 48]. The mannose receptor present on the membrane of macrophages and liver
177 endothelial cells is responsible for the fast internalization via receptor-assisted endocytosis of
178 glycoprotein having a mannose terminal. Magnusson et al. observed a very prompt receptor-
179 mediated endocytosis of glycoprotein with a mannose terminal (ovalbumin) in sinusoidal
180 endothelial rat liver cells. The authors claimed that the highest K_e was reported with respect
181 to a receptor-mediated endocytosis system^[36]. The plasma membrane of the macrophages
182 expresses a variety of transmembrane receptors viz., Fc-receptors, mannose receptors,
183 scavenger receptors, stearylamine receptors, and integrin, which play crucial roles in different
184 biological events viz., (a) migration, (b) growth, (c) differentiation, (d) activation, (e)
185 endocytosis and (f) antigen recognition in mononuclear phagocyte system. Receptors for
186 mannose are abundant in Kupffer cells, alveolar macrophages, peritoneal macrophages,
187 splenic macrophages and brain macrophages (microglia, astrocytes, and dendritic cells
188 derived from monocyte)^[37a, 49]. The mannose-transmembrane receptor present in dendritic
189 cells and macrophages is a 17d kDa C-type lectin protein^[37b, 50]. These mannose-based
190 receptors fulfill a vital role in modulating the immune response of the host via a strong
191 involvement in phagocytosis, antigen presentation and processing, intracellular signaling and
192 cell migration ^[37c, 38a, 51]. More specifically, a high density of the mannose transmembrane
193 receptors can be observed on the surface of dendritic cells ^[38b, 52]. Liver Kupffer cells also
194 express galactosyl and fucose receptors, which can uptake particles with galactose moieties
195 and fucosylated carriers, respectively^[40-41]. Tumor neoplastic cells have a very high affinity
196 towards sugar moieties like lactose, fructose, galactose, and mannose via lectin-like receptors
197 comprising sugars such as Sialic Lewis-X ^[33b, 44]. Although the lectin receptors discussed here
198 are the ones that are most commonly used in the therapeutic applications, additional
199 receptors are also present in buccal cells, oral epithelium, conjunctiva and corneal epithelium
200 [42-43].

201

202 Glyco-conjugation strategies

203 Researchers have used different glycoengineering approaches to functionalize biomaterials
204 for various applications such as vaccine preparation, antibody effector and other immune
205 functions, reducing the toxicity of biomaterial and host tissue response, etc. Conjugation of
206 sugar on a biomaterial surface can be achieved by several means ^[53]. The chemoselective
207 coupling reaction is usually performed to alter the sugar molecule for sugar conjugation.
208 Properties of final sugar conjugates such as saccharide length, sugars' modification pattern
209 (for example O-acetylation), type of carrier protein and saccharide/protein ratio, linkers and
210 conjugation chemistry finally utilized for coupling reaction are significantly relevant for
211 immunogenic point of view. The selection of appropriate natural or chemically modified sugar
212 moiety and available functional groups in the biomaterial are the two fundamental pillars of
213 this process. In some cases, chemical activation of sugar might be required for successful
214 grafting. The activation of sugar can be achieved by using non-selective techniques (see ref
215 53 and references therein) such as targeting hydroxyl groups in a random manner with (a)
216 cyanilating agents used to create cyanide groups for chemical reaction with hydrazines or
217 amines, or (b) carboimidazole used to add carboxyl moieties for further reaction with
218 ethylenediamine ^[53-54]. This can also be obtained using more chemo-selective techniques such
219 as periodate oxidation of *cis*-diols in the carbohydrate ring or at the sialic acid's glycerol
220 moiety to produce aldehydes or sialic or uronic acid's carboxyl groups activation.

221 For reducing steric hindrance between saccharide and other macromolecules (e.g. protein),
222 chemical handles can be inserted using a linker for conjugation. ϵ -amine of lysine residue is
223 usually reacted with the oligosaccharides with end terminal aldehydes. Alternatively,
224 ammonium salts can be used to perform reductive amination to derivatize with di-hydrazide
225 spacers or to deliver an amine for a coupling reaction^[53]. The chemically inserted amine can
226 be openly reacted with proteins' carboxylic acid groups or can be coupled to the different
227 linker with bifunctionality to integrate maleimide, squaric ester, alkyne or azide moieties, thiol
228 to support conjugation. Synthetic sugar with reactive groups viz., alkenes or thiols, amine can
229 be used for aldehyde generation.

230 Broadly, sugar conjugation can be classified into two categories; random and site-selective
231 conjugation. In random conjugation, one of the widely used technique is to graft sugar
232 moieties onto the amine functional group present on biomaterial surface. This can be

233 achieved by coating the biomaterial with amino acids (glutamic, aspartic or lysine) (Figure 3)
234 using covalent or non-covalent process. Because of the hydrophilic nature of the amine
235 groups, it is abundantly exposed/available on the surface of the biomaterials making the
236 process significantly smoother. In some cases, linkers with exposed functional groups such as
237 alkynes, azides, maleimides and hydrazides, may be needed to conjugate natural or activated
238 sugar onto the biomaterial surface^[53]. We would like to refer the readers to the ref. 55 for a
239 more detailed review on this topic^[55]. Site-selective coupling is usually accomplished by
240 targeting highly nucleophilic residues present on the material surface. To achieve such
241 conjugations, materials can be functionalized with functional groups such as thiols, hydroxyls,
242 amines, azides, amidines or their derivatives. These highly nucleophilic groups successively
243 react with a variety of electrophilic reagents, including saccharide derivatives functionalized
244 with thio, selenoether, maleimides or haloalkyl groups which results in the formation of
245 glycoconjugates^[56]. Chemo-selective ligation is forthcoming as a promising method for the
246 site-selective conjugation of carbohydrates and highly functionalized substrates such as
247 proteins. The method involves the reaction of two functionalized groups that have high
248 selective affinity for each other under mild conditions. Researchers have achieved this by
249 using a sulfhydryl group which has high nucleophilicity in contrast to other functionalized
250 groups^[57]. Anomeric oxygen of O-glycopeptide is replaced by sulfur or nitrogen, to form S-
251 and N-linked glycoconjugate^[58]. The modification is not only biocompatible but is also less
252 prone to acid/base or enzyme-mediated hydrolysis. Thio-oligosaccharides thus formed, can
253 be conjugated with different functional groups on proteins and other functionalized
254 substrates to synthesize glycoconjugates.

255 In highly functionalized materials such as proteins, to carry out a selective reaction and obtain
256 a homogeneous product, the cysteine residue can be attached to the electrophilic chemical
257 handle, like a bromooxetane^[59] or a bromoisobutylene^[60] which protects the thiol group of
258 the cysteine and undergoes the halogen displacement with a thiosugar. One of the ways to
259 modify the sulfur group present on cysteine is by using the organoselenium compound –
260 selenyl bromide - to form a stable intermediate under mild conditions^[61]. The intermediate
261 further reacts with thio-oligosaccharides to form glycoprotein with the disulphide bond.
262 Similarly, bis-alkylation-elimination can be used to convert cysteine into dehydroalanine. In a
263 wide array of protein modification reactions, dehydroalanine acts as a synthetic precursor. To

264 form glycoprotein, the cysteine converted into dehydroalanine can undergo a Michael
265 addition reaction with thiosugar^[62] or aza-Michael addition reaction with alkylamine linked
266 carbohydrates^[63]. The cysteine group is, therefore, an important site for the modification of
267 proteins^[53] and attachment of the cysteine-mimicking group on scaffolds will be useful for
268 facilitating the conjugation of material with glycan moiety.

269 Disulfide bonds present in proteins help to stabilize the protein structure^[53]. However, it is
270 possible to cleave the disulphide bond temporarily to attach two cysteines by forming a short
271 covalent bridge. This reaction can be used for glycoconjugation by functionalizing the bridge
272 with carbohydrates^[64]. Furthermore, Triazolinediones can be used to attach phenol
273 functionalized substrates to sugar molecules^[65]. Enzymatic modification of substrates is
274 possible by incorporating a short amino acid tag either on the substrate or on the sugar to be
275 conjugated^[66].

276 Moreover, thiol click-chemistry reactions are nowadays being used for easy, metal-free
277 modification of thiol groups. The avoidance of potentially toxic metal catalysts decreases the
278 biotoxicity of the reaction products and the high heterolytic and homolytic reactivity of thiols
279 towards many functional groups avoids the need for orthogonality (a requisite for efficient
280 click-chemistry reaction) unnecessary. Thiol-ene coupling (TEC) reaction involves radical
281 alkenes hydrothiolation in the presence of radical sources^[67]. The sulfanyl radicals (RS[•]) are
282 added to carbon-carbon double bonds in an anti-Markovnikov fashion. The reaction is mild
283 and uses benign catalysts and solvents along with providing high reaction rates, high yield and
284 complete regio-selectivity. Though TEC reaction undergoes faster addition reaction^[68], it is
285 usually reversible in nature and hence significant excess starting products are required to shift
286 the equilibrium towards sulphide products^[69]. To overcome this obstacle, thio-yne coupling
287 (TYC) reaction is emerging as a promising click chemistry reaction for
288 replacing/complementing existing thiol click chemistry reactions. Similar to TEC, TYC follows
289 anti-Markovnikov addition but the stereoselectivity is lost in the process in the case of TYC.
290 TYC reactions are efficient when carried out at equimolar concentrations of reagents as the
291 intermediate vinyl radicals formed are irreversible in nature and are more reactive than alkyl
292 radicals.

293 The thiol group is widely explored as a functional group for glycoconjugation of a substrate,
294 especially in vaccines and antibodies; however, functional groups such as amine, azide and
295 triazolinediones have also been exploited for the glycoconjugation of the materials^[53].

Figure 3: Glyco-conjugation strategies for functional materials. The figure illustrates different glycoengineering strategies for the functionalization of materials with suitable carbohydrate moiety. The selection of appropriate sugar molecule and functional group are essential and can be decided based on the target tissue/cell and the biomaterial in consideration. Broadly, glyco-conjugation strategies can be divided into two groups – random and selective. The type of conjugation strategy can be selected based on the desired application of the final glycoconjugate.

296 **Engineering of glycans for therapeutic application**

297 In spite of the initial clinical success of sugar-based therapeutic agents in the early
298 20th century, the later progress of the carbohydrate engineering field was fraught with
299 complications. Chemists failed to discover a proper synthesis technique to produce a bulk
300 quantity of carbohydrates for biological analysis whereas the separation procedures for
301 heterogeneous natural sugars using analytical chemistry tools were still at an early stage. A
302 discovery relating to the specific glycan structures in the second part of the twentieth century
303 led to the advent of glycobiology as an independent research field [3a, 3b]. Afterward,
304 researchers started to use this information to engineer glycans for therapeutic applications.

305
306 Figure 4: Chemical structure of commercially available / pre-clinical small molecule
307 glycoengineered drugs that are derived from natural sources. (a) GMI-1070 used to treat
308 sickle cell anemia, (b) Fondaparinux used as an anticoagulating agent, (c) Miglustat used to
309 treat Gaucher disease, (d) Neomycin acts as an antibiotic and is used to prevent bacterial

310 infection, (e) Zanamivir used to prevent viral infection, (f) Oseltamivir used to prevent viral
311 infection and (g) Militol used to treat diabetics.

312

313 **Small molecule glycoengineered drugs**

314 To the present time, most small-molecule glycoengineered drugs have been glycosidase
315 inhibitors or lectins (Figure 4) ^[7, 70]. The most popular drugs to come from glycoengineered
316 carbohydrate compounds have been anti-viral drugs such as oseltamivir (Tamiflu; Figure
317 4f ^[70a]) and zanamivir (Relenza, Figure 4e)^[71]. The influenza virus's life cycle includes the
318 attachment of hemagglutinin (HA) to the sialic acid containing polysaccharide present on the
319 cell surface of the host. These polysaccharides assist viral neuraminidase (NA) by providing a
320 substrate that ensures the maturation and release of the virus ^[72]. Oseltamivir and Zanamivir
321 bind with NA in nanomolar affinity and prohibit the viral entry inside cells as well as viral
322 budding ^[73]. Resistance towards Tamiflu has provided the motivation necessary to develop a
323 novel drug molecule targeting the influenza virus. Incidentally, a difluorinated covalent NA
324 inhibitor has lately been designed by Withers and coworkers^[74].

325 For controlling the levels of blood sugar, another successful glycoengineered compounds are
326 the diabetes mellitus type II drugs viz., (a) acarbose (Precose, Glucobay) and (b) miglitol
327 (Glyset), which can inhibit amylases and glucosidases in the gut, respectively (Figure 4g).
328 Actelion designs N-butyl-deoxynojirimycin-based drug (Miglustat, Zavesca, Figure 4c). It is
329 mainly applied to cure the Gaucher disease. Butters and Dwek initially prepared Miglustat,
330 which is an imino-based sugar. It was observed that the native deoxynojirimycin's N-alkylated
331 analogs acted as efficient inhibitors for the glucosyltransferase produced from
332 glucosylceramide^[75]. It was found that miglustat treatment could increase the concentration
333 of sphingolipid in Gaucher disease. Lectins are one of the factors that play a vital part in
334 managing the bacterial attachment to the host cells and therefore several research groups
335 have focused on the design and development of glycan-based compounds for inhibiting this
336 interaction^[7, 76]. After screening, the most effective compound was tested for its binding
337 affinity towards virulence factors FimH of *Escherichia. coli* and PA-III & PA-IL of *Pseudomonas*
338 *aeruginosa*. Both of these bacteria are categorized as adaptable microbes with a growing
339 antibiotic-resistance nature.

340 In 1982, Thunberg et al. elucidated the structure of heparin, the most celebrated clinical
341 GAG^[77]. This enabled Linhardt et al. to synthesize a heparin derived pentasaccharide in a fully
342 active form^[78]. The reporting of this led to the design and chemical synthesis of the first
343 defined small compound fondaparinux, heparin(ARIXTRA, Figure 4b), which came on the
344 market in 2002 ^[79]. Fondaparinux has successfully reduced the risk of heparin-induced
345 thrombocytopenia mainly because of its small size and longer half-life ^[80]. In 2011, Xu et al.
346 reported the chemoenzymatic synthesis process for the heparin pentasaccharide ^[81]. The
347 significance of preparing well-defined heparin for the therapeutic application was highlighted
348 in 2008 because of the contamination due to the oversulfated version of chondroitin sulfate
349 which resulted in a health catastrophe at an international level ^[82]. An analogous method was
350 used by Copeland et al. to create 3-O-sulfated heparin octasaccharide which blocks the
351 admission of Herpes simplex virus type 1 into the cell^[83].

352 In the later 1980s, selectins' discovery was a prime milestone in the field of glycobiology. It
353 stimulated several decades of novel therapeutic agents' progress. These play a vital role in
354 controlling the movement of leukocytes to the inflammation site by binding with the
355 carbohydrate structures of sialyl Lewis^a (sLe^a) and sialyl Lewis^x (sLe^x)^[84]. Apart from trafficking
356 leucocytes into the inflammation site^[85], sLe^x also plays an important role in the migration of
357 tumors ^[86]. Recently, it was reported that it also acts as a ligand for the binding of human
358 sperm to the zona pellucida in the course of fertilization^[87]. Most of the clinical trials for small
359 molecule-based glycan structures like Cylexin (CY-1503) were stopped in spite of the early
360 enthusiasm in the field of small molecule glycoengineering^[88]. However, during clinical trials
361 for vaso-occlusive crisis (sickle cell anemia, GMI-1070, Figure 4a), asthma treatment
362 (Bimosiamose, TBC-1269), fucosylated mimics of the Lewis compounds showed favorable
363 progress ^[89]. Recently, the Ernst research group has designed ligands attached with a sLe^x
364 construct conjugated with a second site ligand after virtually screening with a nuclear
365 magnetic resonance-guided fragment^[90]. This method allowed the application of E-selectin
366 inhibitors in nano-molar concentration, even though most of these antagonists are yet to be
367 examined in an animal model.

368 N-acetylglucosamine prepared by O-GlcNAcylation has also drawn the interest of scientists
369 owing to its improved regulation in obesity, cancer, Alzheimer's disease and diabetes ^[91]. The
370 modification process of O-GlcNAcylation is usually controlled by O-GlcNAcase (OGA) and

371 diphosphate-N-acetyl-D-glucosamine: polypeptide transferase (OGT), which respectively
372 remove and add the O-GlcNAc molecule from Thr and Ser residues. The David Vocadlo
373 research group has a selective and low nano-molar inhibitor for OGA, thiamet-G^[92]. They
374 observed an increasing level of O-GlcNAcylation in the rodent brain after treatment with
375 thiamet-G followed by a reduction in tau aggregation as well as neuronal cell loss in an
376 Alzheimer's disease mouse model ^[92].

377 In the glycan chemical space, new approaches have been employed to fabricate carbohydrate
378 scaffolds for screening the more potent lectin inhibitors involved in diseased condition ^[93].
379 Apart from the compounds mentioned above, many materials are glycosylated in nature
380 which affects their specificity and efficacy for therapeutic application. The rich field
381 constituted by these compounds is, however, outside the scope of this review ^[94].

382 Apart from the use of glycans to engineer small molecule drugs, glycosylated nanocarriers are
383 being widely used to enhance the targeting abilities of pre-existing small molecule drugs
384 which also results in an increase in circulation times of the drug *in vivo* and a reduction in the
385 systemic side effects^[95]. The glycosylated nanocarrier systems are discussed in detail in
386 another section.

Table 2: Advances in small molecule glycan-based drugs and polyvalent glycan-based inhibitors

Small molecule glycan-based drugs									
Product name	Acronym	Elimination half-life	Route of administration	Developed by	Mode of action	Target /species	Disease	Side effect/Tested on	Ref
Oseltamivir	Tamiflu	1–3 hours, 6–10 hours (active metabolite)	Oral, inhalation	Gilead Sciences	Stop the viral entry inside cells and viral budding	Virus	Influenza (A&B)	Vomiting, diarrhea, headache, and trouble sleeping etc.	[70a]
Zanamivir	Relenza	2.5–5.1 hours	Oral, inhalation	Peter Colman and Joseph Varghese	Stop the viral entry inside cells and viral budding	Virus	Influenza (A&B)	Headache, dizziness, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea etc.	[71]
Acarbose	Precose, Glucobay	2 hours	Oral	Bayer AG	Inhibit amylases and glucosidases in the gut	NA	Diabetes mellitus type II	Flatulence and diarrhea	[96]
Miglitol	Glyset	2 hours	Oral	Bayer AG	Inhibit amylases and glucosidases in the gut	NA	Diabetes mellitus type II	Flatulence and diarrhea	[96]
N-butyl-deoxynojirimycin	Miglustat, Zavesca	6–7 hours	Oral	Butters and Dwek	Inhibit glucosyltransferase	NA	Gaucher disease	Diarrhea, stomach pain or bloating, gas, loss of appetite etc.	[75, 96]
Heparin/fondaparinux	Arixtra	17-21 hours	Subcutaneous	Mclean	Anticoagulant	NA	Deep vein thrombosis	Vomiting, skin rash, headache etc.	[80] [77]
Rivipansel	GMI-1070	8 hours	Intravenously	Glycomimetics	Inhibits the interaction between leukocytes and the endothelium	NA	Sickle cell anemia	No adverse side effect	[89]
Bimosiamose	TBC-1269	3-4 hours	Inhalation	Encysive Pharmaceutical	Pan-selectin antagonist	NA	Asthma treatment	Mild discomfort, cramping etc.	[89, 96]
Neomycin	NA	2 to 3 hours	Oral, intravenous, topical	Selman Waksman	Protein synthesis Inhibitors	Bacteria	Antibiotic	Tinnitus, hearing loss, and vestibular problems	[96]

Kanamycin	NA	2 hours 30 minutes	Oral, intravenous, topical	Hamao Umezawa	Protein synthesis Inhibitors	Bacteria	Antibiotic	Loss of hearing, toxicity to kidneys, etc.	[96]
Gentamicin	NA	2 hours	Oral, intravenous, topical	Wagman et al.	Protein synthesis Inhibitors	Bacteria	Antibiotic	Low blood cell counts, Neuromuscular problems, Nerve damage, Kidney damage, Ear disorders	[96]
Polyvalent glycan-based inhibitors									
Oligovalent dendrimer	STARFISH	NA	NA	Kitov et al.	Inhibition towards Shiga like toxin, enterotoxin and cholera toxin	Bacteria	Cholera and <i>E. Coli</i> infection	E.Coli	[96-97]
Dendrimers with the sialic acid containing Pentasaccharide	GM1	NA	NA	Pukin et al., Sisu et al.	High <i>in vitro</i> binding affinity towards toxins as well as inhibition of cellular toxicity	Bacteria	Cholera and <i>E. Coli</i> infection	Endothelial cells	[98]
Sulfated lactose PEO star dendrimer	NA	NA	NA	Rele et al.	Bind with selectins with high affinity and can reduce acute inflammation	Inflammatory cell	Inflammatory diseases	Mouse	[99]
Glyconanoparticles conjugated with sle ^x	NA	NA	NA	Van Kasteren et al.	Sle ^x to bind with multimeric selectin	<i>In vivo</i> imaging	Cerebral inflammation, multiple sclerosis	Wistar rats	[100]
Oligomannose Dendron	NA	NA	NA	Wang et al.	Blocking the active site of HIV by mannose dendrimers conjugated dendrimer	Virus	HIV	Dendritic cells	[101]
Q β glycodendronan particle	NA	NA	NA	Rendle Et al.	Prevent the Ebola infection of dendritic cells by blocking the binding of viral component to DC-SIGN	Virus	Ebola	Dendritic cells	[102]
Lipid nanoparticles	NA	NA	NA	O'Reilly and Paulson	Targeted cancer therapy using for new	Tumor cells	Cancer	Mice	[103]

					sialoside-based ligand for targeting Siglecs				
Glycopolymer-based system	NA	NA	NA	Kitov et al.	Upgraded STARFISH inhibitor by synthesizing a glycopolymer-based system comprise of Pk glycan conjugated (S)-polybait	Bacteria	Cholera and <i>E. Coli</i> infection	Transgenic mice	[104]
Glycomethanet hiosulphonates (glyco-MTS) ligation technology	MTS	NA	NA	Davis et al.	Site-dependently attach a sulfated tyrosine and sle ^x into the ssβg, bacterial enzyme	Bacteria	Inflammatory diseases	Rat	[105]
GAG-based glycopolymer	NA	NA	NA	Hsieh-Wilson group	Chemically prepared ROMP-CS mimics can prevent the outgrowth of neurite	NA	Wound healing, Neuro-inflammation	Mouse	[106]
Synthetic 4- and 6-position of the Galactosamine within CS	Anti-CS-E	NA	NA	Brown et al.,	Antibody against CS-E showed axon regeneration	NA	Neuro degenerative disease	Mouse	[107]

387 **Polyvalent glycoengineered molecules and inhibitors**

388 The major difficulty when targeting monovalent glycans (small molecules) is that their binding
389 affinity towards lectin is quite low and so they cannot be designated as appropriate drug
390 candidates. Keeping this drawback in mind, researchers from polymer and carbohydrate
391 chemistry backgrounds have designed multivalent glycoconjugates, taking advantage of the
392 popular “cluster glycoside effect” to improve lectin avidity^[108]. There are essentially three
393 types of macromolecular glycosylated structures viz., (a) glycopolymers, (b)
394 glyconanoparticles, and (c) glycodendrimers^[108a, 109]. While most of these synthesized
395 materials are still in the development stage with respect to biological evaluation, they
396 symbolize the next-generation movement of glycotherapeutics technologies. Arguably,
397 glycodendrimer is the most clinically favorable scaffold ^[109a, 110]. A dendrimer is a global
398 moiety having a single molecular weight. They typically comprise a central zone, branched
399 layers and several end groups with different functionalization^[111]. One of the very first
400 glycodendrimer synthesis was reported by Yuan et al. ^[112]. However, STARFISH was the first
401 therapeutically significant development of an oligovalent dendron-like complex having
402 analogs of Gb3 trisaccharide (Pk) covalently linked to the pentavalent glucose moiety (Figure
403 5b). It is well known that Gb3 carbohydrate is a ligand for the *E. coli*-based Shiga-like
404 contaminants. The *in vitro* inhibition towards Shiga-like toxin captured via the oligovalent
405 display of Pk in STARFISH was 1–10⁶ times more than all well-known ligands with a univalent
406 nature ^[97]. Researchers have tried similar mechanisms to deactivate heat-labile enterotoxin
407 and cholera toxin ^[96]. Dendrimers with a sialic acid moiety conjugated with oligosaccharide-
408 GM1 were synthesized and significantly high *in vitro* binding affinity towards toxins as well as
409 inhibition of cellular toxicity was observed ^[98].

410

411 Figure 5. Chemical structure of polyvalent glycoengineered molecules and inhibitors for
 412 targeting lectins. (a) Sulfated-lactose based PEO star dendrimer system is used to inhibit
 413 selectins and reduce acute inflammation, (b) STARFISH used as an efficient inhibitor for E.coli
 414 based Shiga-like toxins, (c) sLe^x-Iron oxide nanoparticle used to image selectins, (d) (S)-poly-
 415 BAIT, a cyclic pyruvate ketal capable of binding with Shiga-like toxins for clearance process,
 416 (e) SET-LRP based glycopolymer system with measured optimization towards binding of DG-
 417 SIGN molecule, (f) Q β glycodendronan particles prevent the Ebola infection of dendritic cells

418 by blocking the binding of viral component to DC-SIGN, (g) High mannose-based dendrimer
419 blocks the active site of HIV using mannose residue, (h) Antibody against chondroitin sulfate-
420 E showed neuronal healing properties in terms of axon regeneration, (i) Lipid-based
421 nanoparticle for targeted cancer therapy using new sialoside-based ligand for targeting
422 Siglecs.

423 Scientists have used dendrimer-based systems to image or block sugar-binding proteins in
424 mammals. Chaikof and associates showed that the highly sulfated lactose ligands associated
425 poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) star dendrimer can bind with selectins with high affinity and can
426 reduce acute inflammation in a mouse model^[99] (Figure 5a). Glyconanoparticles consisting of
427 chemically crosslinked amine-functionalized iron oxide were conjugated with sLe^x to bind
428 with multimeric selectin (Figure 5c). Iron oxide is a well-known contrast agent for MRI and the
429 feature of the engineered particle to specifically direct selectin proteins have allowed imaging
430 of the inflammation of the brain in stroke and multiple sclerosis in animal models^[100]. CD209,
431 the dendritic cell-specific intracellular adhesion molecule grabbing non-integrin (DG-SIGN), is
432 a standard target for dendrimer-based materials because of its role in the efficient binding of
433 a wide variety of pathogens. It is a C-type lectin-based transmembrane receptor present on
434 both dendritic cells and macrophages. To spread and evade the immune system, it can
435 effectively bind with Ebola, Mycobacterium tuberculosis and HIV i.e. an escape mechanism
436 for the pathogen^[102]. During 2008, Wang et al. fabricated an oligomannose dendron-based
437 system that can effectively inhibit the binding of a recombinant dimeric version of DG-SIGN
438 with respect to IC50 value and gp120, the mannosylated envelop protein of HIV to anti-HIV
439 antibodies^[101a]. Following this, many other groups have also shown successful inhibition of
440 HIV trans-infection by blocking the active site of HIV by mannose dendrimer-conjugated
441 nanoparticles^[101b]. Recent reports have also shown that a high concentration of mannose
442 dendrimer can efficiently inhibit the HIV infection which is mediated by DG-SIGN at the
443 cellular level as well as in human uterine cervix explant models (Figure 5g)^[113].

444 Rendle et al. showed a highly valent “glycodendriprotein”-based system by conjugating
445 glycodendrimers on the multiple sites of a protein^[114]. This strategy was used to attach
446 mannose dendrimers onto the icosahedrons of Q β . The consequential construct of
447 “glycodendronanoparticles” is observed as the utmost highly valent glycodendrimeric system
448 regardless of its diameter of 32 nm with respect to 1,620 carbohydrate units (Figure 5f).

449 Ribeiro-Viana et. al. showed that these supervalent components were able to effectively
450 remove the infection of Ebola through blocking the mechanism of viral binding to DG-
451 SIGN^[115]. García-Vallejo et al. prepared a tetrasaccharide Leb (DC-SIGN ligand) conjugated
452 poly(amidoamine) (PAMAM) dendrimer-based system to increase the vaccine's delivery to
453 the dendritic cells (DCs)^[116]. Singh et al. showed that these dendrimers formed stronger DC
454 activation as well as producing subsequent stimulation of T cells over that of previous
455 conjugates of Lewis polysaccharide to the OVA peptide alone when they bind with the OVA
456 protein as an antigen ^[117].

457 Sialic acid-binding immunoglobulin-like lectins (Siglecs) are another category of
458 transmembrane cell surface receptors present in hematopoietic cells and is considered as a
459 promising candidate for cancer therapy and other drug delivery applications ^[103a, 103b]. Paulson
460 and coworkers have created a library of diversified sialoside for identifying new sugar-based
461 ligand for targeting Siglecs^[103c, 103d]. For directing lipid nanoparticles and toxic virus-like
462 particles towards the particular lymphomas and leukocytes, they used these specific ligands
463 based on their Siglac expression^[118] (Figure 5I). In the areas of targeted cancer therapy and
464 targeted gene delivery, these methodologies provide support and new targets for current
465 efforts.

466 The research group of Kiessling has contributed significantly to the field of glycopolymers,
467 reporting that the molecular structure of multivalent ligands is a prime feature that governs
468 the activity. However, the additionally designed construct can be needed in some cases for
469 enhancing the specificity and avidity^[119]. Based on this concept, the Bundle research group
470 upgraded their previously reported STARFISH inhibitor by synthesizing a glycopolymer-based
471 system that comprises Pk glycan conjugated (S)-PolyBAIT, a cyclic pyruvate ketal (CP) (Figure
472 5d)^[104]. CP is a well-known ligand of the serum amyloid P component (SAP), capable of
473 targeting the attached binders for the clearance process. It also plays a critical part in clearing
474 the Shiga-like toxin. This polymer is injected intravenously in mice and later a fatal amount of
475 Shiga-like toxin I was injected subcutaneously and zero percent mortality was observed.
476 Fascinatingly, mice that were injected intravenously with a copolymer having randomly
477 distributed CP and Pk showed severe Shigatoxemia signs. These reports show the growing
478 importance of conjugating ligand on polymeric constructs for trafficking necessary proteins
479 to improve drug efficacy and toxin clearance.

480 Reporting the further importance of attaching ligand onto glycan scaffold, Davis and
481 coworkers prepared a synthetic ligand mimicking the P-selectin-glycoprotein-ligand-1. They
482 used a combination of copper-catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition and ligation method of
483 glycomethanethiosulphonates to site-dependently attach a sulfated tyrosine and sLe^x into the
484 SSβG, bacterial enzyme ^[105a]. These two components play an important role in site-specific
485 binding to P-selectin. In a chronically inflamed rat cortex model, this modified SSβG with lacZ-
486 type galactosidase property can be utilized to stain the P-selectin^[105b].

487 The Hsieh-Wilson group has established the synthetic preparation of GAG glycopolymer
488 mimics using ROMP because isolation of a homogeneous version of native GAGs from natural
489 sources is quite challenging. Previous reports have shown that the chondroitin sulfate's (CS)
490 sulfation pattern plays a crucial role in controlling the healing mechanism in the nervous
491 system. However, it is restricted by the process of critically controlled sulfation patterns of
492 CS^[120]. The Hsieh-Wilson group reported that the chemically synthesized ROMP-CS mimics
493 can inhibit the outgrowth of neurite ^[106] and, in the follow-up article, they identified the
494 reason for this activity as 4- & 6-position sulfation of galactosamine unit in CS (Figure 5h) ^[107].
495 Chemical synthesis of GAGs has allowed this research group to produce a CS-E epitope-
496 specific antibody that could stimulate the revival process of axon in a mice model with a glial
497 wound in the optic neuron.

498 The space of glycopolymer is currently driven by the application of recently developed
499 methods of controlled radical polymerization, allowing the generation of highly defined
500 polymer structures ^[121]. However, most of these materials were not tested properly for their
501 biological efficacy. The Haddleton research group has recently shown a technique to prepare
502 a linear copolymer using single-electron transfer living radical polymerization (SET-LRP),
503 where the sugar position can be controlled for the first time (Figure 5e)^[122]. They have
504 reported the synthesis of multi-block glycopolymers with the monomer of acrylate containing
505 glucose, fucose and mannose residues and showed that the only structure of mannose
506 monomer clustered in a certain way can bind to DG-SIGN.

507 **Glycan-based vaccines**

508 Glycan-based vaccines played a very crucial role in bringing carbohydrate chemistry into the
509 limelight of relevant clinical platforms ^[8b, 123]. Numerous currently available vaccines are

510 based on carbohydrates viz., (a) Prevnar (*Streptococcus pneumonia*), (b) Menactra (*Neisseria*
511 *meningitides*), (c) Hib (*Haemophilus influenzae* type b), and (d) TYPHIM Vi (*Salmonella*
512 *typhi*)^[123a, 124]; though these products are first isolated from natural sources and then
513 nonspecifically conjugated with carrier proteins. In this review, we are focusing on the recent
514 advances in glycoengineered synthetic vaccines, which have therapeutic potential that is
515 more distinct. Development in the area of protein conjugation chemistry has significantly
516 influenced the methods available to a glycan-based vaccine that can selectively conjugate
517 with protein carriers^[56, 125]. Detailed progress of glycan-based vaccines for bacteria^[126],
518 cancer^[30b, 127] and HIV^[128] is reviewed by several research groups.

519

520 Figure 6: Chemical structure of commercially available and pre-clinical glycan-based vaccines.

521 (a) Vaccine against cancer-related polysaccharide epitopes, (b) Vaccine against *Shigella*

522 flexneri, (c) Vaccine against *Haemophilus influenza*, (d) Vaccine against *Plasmodium*
523 *falciparum*, (e) Vaccine against HIV and (f) Vaccine against *Candida albicans*

524 The Cuban Hib vaccine is by far the most successful and the first clinically approved candidate
525 that is a completely synthetic glycan-based vaccine inspired by capsular polysaccharide
526 antigen's structure of Hib (figure 6c)^[129]. Pentasaccharide-tetanus toxin (TT) is produced in
527 larger quantity in the GMP facility so that it can be fused to the current routine system of
528 vaccination in Cuba. Seeberger et al. used a similar tactic to prepare an antimalarial vaccine
529 using an automated chemical synthesis method of the glycosylphosphatidylinositol (GPI),
530 isolated from *Plasmodium falciparum* (Malaria) (Figure 6d)^[130]. In the mice model, Tamborrini
531 et al. observed that the treated animal showed improved survival as well as protection against
532 various disease symptoms observed during malaria parasite infection such as pulmonary
533 edema, cerebral syndrome, malarial acidosis, and death. They also productively prepared a
534 vaccine for *Bacillus anthracis* using the spore tetrasaccharide to develop antibodies against
535 anthrax for imaging and detection purposes ^[131].

536 Mulard and associates used the three repeating units of *Shigella flexneri* 2a LPS' O-specific
537 polysaccharide domain to prepare a synthetic version of pentadecasaccharide (Figure 6b).
538 This carbohydrate conjugated tetanus toxoid (TT) showed the improved response of anti-LPS
539 2a antibody in serum in a mice model compared to a small length of synthetic O-specific
540 polysaccharide sequences^[132]. After immunization, the mice synthesized anti-LPS antibodies
541 (glycoconjugate-induced) which provided protection during SF2a infection. Based on pre-
542 clinical data, Phalipon et al. showed that these results are also valid for treatment in humans
543 ^[133]. Unlike previous developments, which were typically conjugation methods based on
544 monovalent epitopes, the modern approach is to utilize the constructs of a multivalent
545 epitope. β -mannan trisaccharide epitope attached polymer which was isolated from the cell
546 wall of *Candida albicans* chemically attached with chicken serum albumin showed
547 significantly higher antibody production in a mice model compared to the trisaccharide-TT
548 vaccine^[134]. Later, Bundle and associates used this IgG to classify a vaccine with minimal
549 disaccharide epitope to protect the *C. albicans* infected rabbit (Figure 6f)^[135]. Reports from
550 Nifantiev and Pier labs showed that a number of synthetic glycan-based vaccines can detect
551 the β -(1 \rightarrow 6)-poly-*N*-acetyl-d-glucosamine (PNAG) which is a basic component of various
552 pathogenic bacteria's capsular polysaccharide. Antibodies isolated from immunized rabbits

553 were used to protect *S. aureus* and *E. coli* infected mice ^[136]. Over the past decade, a major
554 focus of glycobiology research was to target the high mannose (Man₉ carbohydrate) domain
555 of gp120, the envelope protein of HIV via roughly neutralizing antibodies ^[137]. One of the most
556 popular candidates is the 2G12 clone which deactivates via deceleration of the admission
557 process of the virus into the host cells. After the passive transfer of the virus into patients, it
558 can also hinder the replication of the virus ^[75b]. Another successful example is the PG9 clone
559 which can bind to the carbohydrates present in both gp 140 and gp 120 envelope protein^[138].
560 During the early stages of HIV vaccine development, researchers tried to induce an immune
561 response by targeting the gp120's high mannose epitope in bovine serum albumin conjugate
562 in a rabbit model. However, they observed that the antibodies produced showed neither an
563 affinity towards native gp120 N-glycans nor a deactivation of the virus^[139].

564 Based on these background findings, the Davis research group developed a vaccine using a
565 synthetic equivalent of mannose to produce a non-self-epitope with more immunogenic
566 properties (Figure 6e). Doores et al. showed that this synthetic mannose analog conjugated
567 virus-like particle Q β has a high binding affinity towards 2G12 and can cause a better
568 antibody-mediated immune response that is only comparable to the native mannose
569 conjugated vaccines ^[140]. Rabbits were immunized to produce an antibody that can bind to
570 the cowpea mosaic virus conjugated with Man₈ and Man₉. However, these antibodies showed
571 no affinity towards gp120 or a decrease in virus infection indicating that the carrier protein
572 also plays a crucial role in neutralizing antibody production. Aussedat et al. recently showed
573 the synthesized glycopeptide having two closely spaced N-glycans at Asn¹⁵⁶ and Asn¹⁶⁰ of
574 gp120 that can bind more strongly with PG9 antibody than to glycan alone as a ligand ^[141].

575 Several research groups have observed the changes in glycosylation of transformed cancer
576 cells^[142]. It was noted that the changes in glycosylation tend to increase in the case of highly
577 sialylated and branched constructs which is usually followed by a rise in mucinous proteins
578 viz., MUC16 and MUC1^[143]. For cancer vaccine, tumor-associated carbohydrate antigens
579 (TACAs) and unique repeated glycan epitopes have been a major target^[144] (Figure 6a). Being
580 an early pioneer in the field, Danishefsky et al. developed the first synthetic-based Globo H
581 vaccine for clinical application ^[145]. Later, his research group synthesized the KLH carrier
582 protein conjugated five breasts and prostate cancer-associated glycan-based antigen Tn, TF,
583 Globo-H and GM2^[8a] (Figure 6a). These candidates showed successful IgG/IgM-based

584 immune response in a mice model and currently, in clinical trials. Huang et al. tested different
585 adjuvants as well as carrier proteins expanding the safety profile and immunogenicity to
586 prepare an optimized version of a vaccine against hexasaccharide Globo-H^[146]. A mixture of
587 α -galactosylceramide analog adjuvant and Globo-H attached diphtheria toxoid elicited a
588 strong IgG response against Globo-H as well as against other interrelated compounds
589 specifically observed in cancer stem cell and breast cancer. Ingale et al. reported a multi-
590 component vaccine made of a tumor-associated glycopeptide and a TLR2 agonist that are able
591 to produce a strong IgG response in a mice model which was further identified by the tumor-
592 linked glycans on cancer cells^[147]. Due to the presence of MUC1 in a wide variety of cancers,
593 it was accepted as a cancer vaccine target^[148]. But the initial approaches are mostly
594 dependent on the traditional method of vaccine development using unglycosylated epitopes
595^[145a]. The three-component method consists of the Pam₃CysSK₄ TLR agonist, the T-helper
596 epitope and a GalNAc-glycosylated MUC1 peptide, developed by the Boons research group
597 showed that it could produce a higher IgG response in a mice model, i.e. it could elicit both
598 cellular and humoral immunity^[149]. Wilkinson et al. also developed a self-assembled
599 nanoparticle-based three-component vaccine for adjuvant purposes^[150]. Inspired by the
600 synthetic multivalent based approach, Dumy and associates prepared a regioselectively
601 addressable functionalized templates (RAFT) attached self-adjuvanting glyco-lipopeptides
602^[151]. RAFT is composed of a universal CD4⁺ T-helper epitope and a CD8⁺ T cell epitope and four
603 α -GalNAc molecules (Tn antigen) linked to the Pam adjuvant^[152]. It was observed that this
604 biomaterial elicits a strong IgG/IgM response in a mice model and is able to identify tumor
605 cell lines. It was also found that this construct was able to reduce the size of the tumor in mice
606 that is inoculated using a syngeneic murine cancer cell (MO5). Huang et al. developed a self-
607 adjuvating based system using glycosylated MUC1 peptides attached to self-assembling fibrils
608 from the peptide domain of Q11 which can elicit an adjuvant-free response^[153].

609 **Gene delivery**

610 Gene therapy shows great promise and potential in the treatment of currently incurable
611 genetic and acquired diseases^[154]. However, safe and effectual delivery of therapeutic genes
612 to the desired target remains a fundamental challenge in gene therapy. One of the promising
613 candidates to overcome these issues is polyethylenimine (PEI) which has shown effective
614 endocytotic pathway uptake and endosomal escape capacity along with DNA

615 condensation^[155]. However, researchers have observed that the high transfection efficiency
616 of PEI is allied to a high molecular weight which in turn shows a high cytotoxic effect^[156]. Also,
617 the targeted delivery of DNA with PEI is still a challenge due to the lack of specificity of PEI
618 towards targeted cells. To overcome these issues, PEI was conjugated with mannose which
619 showed higher transfection efficiency, higher cell-specific targeting and reduced toxicity than
620 that of unconjugated PEI^[157].

621 Macrophages are vital to carry out immune functions such as antigen presentation^[158].
622 Targeted delivery of genes to macrophages is a challenge for the treatment of genetic
623 metabolic diseases such as Gaucher's disease or for the inhibition of HIV replication^[159]. The
624 use of non-viral vectors for *in vivo* gene delivery is being considered because of their simplicity
625 and safety over viral vector systems^[160]. Cationic liposomes are among the promising non-
626 viral gene delivery systems; however, they do not exhibit any cell specificity *in vivo*. To
627 overcome this drawback, galactosylated cholesterol-derived gene delivery systems have been
628 synthesized^[161].

629 **Protein and peptide delivery**

630 Proteins and peptides are promising biopharmaceutical drugs in the prevention and cure of
631 numerous diseases. However, the manufacturing and storage of these therapeutics are
632 challenging due to the issues relating to their stability, such as inactivation and aggregation.
633 To resolve the issues pertaining to solid-phase stability of proteins after lyophilization, a
634 chemical glycosylation strategy was applied for the development of a stable formulation of α -
635 chymotrypsin (α -CT)^[162]. A study showed that glycans (lactose and dextran) were covalently
636 attached to the protein (α -CT) surface and prevented the electrostatic reaction between
637 water molecules and interior protein by the formation of steric hindrance. This led to a
638 reduction in the moisture-induced aggregation and activity loss of α -CT regardless of the size
639 of the glycans.

640 One of the hallmarks of cancer is the avoidance of apoptosis^[163]. Cytochrome c (Cyt c), is a
641 small mitochondrial heme protein that activates the intrinsic apoptotic pathway upon the
642 discharge into the cytosol^[164]. In cancer, sustained angiogenesis and insufficient lymphatic
643 damage observed in tumor leads to the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect
644 which is exploited for the accumulation of nanoparticles in tumors^[165]. Mesoporous silica

645 nanoparticles were used for the stimulus-responsive intracellular delivery of Cyt c but the
646 treatment was unsuccessful in the induction of apoptosis in human urine cancer cells ^[166].
647 However, the further study demonstrated that the attachment of lactose to the surface of
648 Cyt c not only improved the apoptotic activity and thermodynamic stability of the drug but
649 also protected the drug from protease degradation.

650 Multifunctional gold glyconanoparticles incorporating sialyl-Tn and Lewis^x antigens, T-cell
651 helper peptides (TT) and glucose were developed as a novel platform for anticancer
652 vaccines^[167]. These multifunctional hybrid nanoparticles with defined average chemical
653 composition were prepared in a one-step procedure. This methodology opens the door for
654 the creation of potential polyvalent vaccine candidates and polyvalent drug carriers with
655 chemically defined average composition^[168].

656 **Diagnostic reagent delivery**

657 Glycosylated nanocarriers have shown great potential as diagnostic tools. Sentinel lymph
658 nodes (SLNs) play an important part in the metastasis of primary tumors as they are the first
659 lymph nodes to be reached by cancer cells during metastasis^[169]. Therefore, the biopsy
660 evaluation of SLNs is important for the determination of tumor metastasis for which the
661 accurate localization of SLNs is required^[170]. To overcome the drawbacks in current imaging
662 methods for SLNs such as non-selective biodistribution, a need for invasive surgery, expensive
663 equipment, and complex preoperative preparation procedures, a new glycoconjugate-based
664 method was developed^[171]. The dextran-based nanogels conjugated with a wide spectra
665 emitting fluorescent agents (FDNGs) were developed with an optimum size for specific SLN
666 imaging^[172]. The results showed that FDNG could be used as highly efficient molecular
667 imaging probes for stable, specific, selective, safe and non-invasive SLN mapping and thus
668 have the potential for use in bioimaging of SLN for detection of cancer metastasis.

669 The recognition, labeling, and imaging of target cells have been widely applied in many areas
670 of medicine and cell biology for the early diagnosis of disease, cancer metastasis, cell
671 development, cell separation and targeted drug delivery^[173]. Magnetic resonance imaging
672 (MRI), an imaging technique, is widely used for the study of neurologic diseases in humans.
673 In brain diseases, antibody-mediated detection of broad-spectrum inflammation biomarkers
674 is being replaced by carbohydrate-mediated detection of brain-specific inflammation markers

675 (such as CD62 proteins) because of the numerous drawbacks associated with the former
676 technique^[174]. The affinity of CD62 proteins for their cognate ligand molecule type,
677 carbohydrate- sialyl Lewis^x (sLe^x), was exploited to design T₂-type nano-sized glycosylated
678 contrast agents GNP-sLe^x ^[100]. This GNP-MRI method selectively detects CD62E as a biomarker
679 which is displayed on the “blood-side” of the blood-brain barrier (BBB) but is indicative of
680 pathology on the “brain-side”. Also, the in vivo model did not show any BBB breakdown and
681 the GNPs efficiently cleared post-detection without the induction of toxicity. Moreover,
682 Galactose conjugated fluorescent nanoparticles have shown promising effectiveness in
683 identifying liver cancer cells in the blood and this was demonstrated by laser confocal
684 scanning microscopy and flow cytometric analysis^[175]. A summary of glycoconjugate
685 nanocarriers used for application in imaging techniques is given in Table 3.

Table 3: Overview of bioimaging nanoscale devices developed using glycans as grafting molecules

Application	Nature of nanoparticle	Binding sugar	Target cells/tissue	Model	Imaging Technique	Properties	Ref
Quantum dots	Cadmium sulfide	Lactobionic acid	Hepatocytes	<i>In vitro</i>	Fluorescence bioimaging	Enhanced biocompatibility	[176]
Contrast enhancer	Dendrimer	Lactobionic acid	HCC	<i>In vivo</i>	Computer tomography	Enhanced biocompatibility and stable colloidal formulation	[177]
	Dendrimer	Lactobionic acid	HCC	<i>In vivo</i>	Computer tomography	High in-vivo biodistribution	[178]
	Fe ₃ O ₄	Lactobionic acid	Hepatocytes	<i>In vivo</i>	Magnetic resonance	High liver specificity, low non-specific distribution	[179]
	Fe ₃ O ₄	Dextran	Brain, tumor cells	<i>In vivo</i>	Magnetic resonance	Specificity to tumor cells and macrophages	[180]
	Fe ₃ O ₄	Lactobionic acid	HCC	<i>In vivo</i>	Magnetic resonance	High colloidal stability, biocompatibility, hemocompatibility	[181]
	Fe ₃ O ₄	Sialyl Lewis ^x (sLe ^x)	Brain inflammation	<i>In vivo</i>	Magnetic resonance	biocompatibility, no blood brain barrier breakage, high specificity	[100]
	Polymeric	Lactobionic acid	HepG2	<i>In vitro</i>	Magnetic resonance	Targeted drug delivery, bioimaging	[182]
Polymeric	Lactobionic acid	Hepatocytes	<i>In vivo</i>	Computer tomography	Specific targeting, Low non-specific distribution	[183]	
Polymeric	Lactobionic acid	Hepatocytes	<i>In vivo</i>	Computer tomography	Enhanced specificity to liver	[184]	
Fluorescent agent	Carbon nanospheres	Lactobionic acid	Hepatocytes	<i>In vitro</i>	Fluorescence bioimaging	Enhanced stability, low cytotoxicity	[185]
	Chitin nanocrystals	Mannose	-	-	Fluorescence bioimaging	Enhanced targetability	[186]
	Nanogels	Dextran	Sentinel lymph nodes	<i>In vivo</i>	Fluorescence bioimaging	specific, stable, selective, non-invasive and safe SLN mapping	[172]
	Liposomes	Mannose	Macrophages	<i>In vivo</i>	PET Imaging	Specific targeting, low non-specific distribution	[187]
	Gold	Lactobionic acid	HepG2	<i>In vitro</i>	Fluorescence bioimaging	Low non-specific targeting	[188]
	Silica	Lactobionic acid	BEL-7404	<i>In vitro</i>	Fluorescence bioimaging	Increased signal amplification, enhanced photostability	[175]
	Polymeric	Lactobionic acid	CHO	<i>In vitro</i>	Fluorescence bioimaging	Increased binding capacity	[189]

686 **Lectin-mediated drug targeting**

687 Targeted delivery of drugs is crucial in enhancing the efficacy of medical therapy. Sugar-
 688 binding proteins – lectins - are expressed on the surface of a large variety of mammalian cells
 689 where they may act as signaling molecules, recognition molecules and adhesion molecules
 690 for the targeted delivery of bioactive components by exploiting their binding affinity to
 691 specific monosaccharides or oligosaccharides. The therapeutic applications of carbohydrates
 692 as a drug carrier system are outlined in Table 4 and are additionally illustrated in Figure 7.

693

694 Figure 7: Graphical illustration of cell surface glycans, lectin receptors and glycan-based
695 therapeutic systems. A) Glycans can be found attached to proteins and lipids on the cell
696 surface. Some of the glyco-conjugates depicted here are glycoproteins and proteoglycans in
697 which glycans are attached to proteins and glycosphingolipids involving lipid-based glyco-
698 conjugates. B) Schematic representation of C-type lectin receptors that bind to carbohydrates
699 in a calcium-dependent manner. Conserved carbohydrate recognition domains mediate the
700 carbohydrate recognition activity of these lectin receptors. C) Glyco-therapeutics can be
701 broadly divided into two subclasses – glycoconjugates as therapeutics and glycoconjugates as
702 systems for therapeutic application.

703

704 **Disease-specific applications of glycoconjugates**

705 **Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV)**

706 Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is a type of RNA virus more specifically known as a
707 retrovirus which causes irreparable damage to the immune system of the host. The
708 antiretroviral drugs synthesized for the treatment of HIV infections have been found
709 successful in inhibiting reverse transcriptase and thus preventing the replication of HIV by
710 halting the synthesis of viral DNA. However, one of the major obstacles in making these drugs
711 available clinically is their dose-limiting toxicity. Recent research shows that this limitation
712 can be overcome by entrapping these drugs in colloidal carrier systems like liposomes which
713 are preferentially uptaken by cells of the mononuclear phagocyte system (MPS) -
714 Macrophages^[190]. Cells of macrophage lineage contribute to the pathogenesis of HIV infection
715 substantially owing to their ability to spread virus particles to CD4-lymphocytes and their
716 explicit dynamics of HIV replication which makes them an ideal target for the delivery of HIV
717 drugs^[191]. It has been observed that the macrophages and the other cells of MPS express
718 various glycan-specific lectin-like receptors such as asialoglycoprotein receptors and Fc
719 receptors on their surface. Thus, when the delivery system is conjugated with a glycan moiety
720 such as mannose, galactose, lactose or fructose, it would effectively deliver the drug to the
721 infected macrophages via the lectin-carbohydrate interaction^[192].

722 When liposomes coated with chemically modified galactose were synthesized, they showed
723 prolonged carrier potential that was greater than the unmodified liposomes with significantly

724 low AZT drug release in 24 h^[193]. Along with sustained drug release, the cellular uptake of the
725 encapsulated drug was significantly increased in the case of glycan-modified liposomes.
726 Similarly, the galactosylated liposomal vesicular system showed prolonged release carrier
727 potential along with the alteration in the biodistribution of the stavudine drug by targeted
728 delivery to liver, spleen, and lungs that was more than that of the uncoated liposomal
729 formulation^[194]. On labeling the drug, plain liposomes and galactosylated liposomes with
730 ^{99m}Tc to study their biodistribution profiles *in vivo*, it was observed that the drug had a very
731 short plasma half-life and this can be increased by using liposomes as they were able to target
732 and be retained in the liver for longer. It was also observed that the galactosylation of
733 liposomes increased their accumulation in liver and decreased the bone-marrow cytotoxicity
734 of the drug^[195]. Liposome systems were also utilized for the delivery of genes to macrophages
735 for the inhibition of DNA replication^[161b]. Although the liposomes showed promising results
736 as non-viral gene delivery vehicles on their own, conjugation with galactose further enhanced
737 their targetability towards macrophages.

738 Dendrimers are actively being used as a controlled and targeted delivery system and one such
739 example is poly (propylene imine) (PPI). PPI dendrimers were synthesized and used for the
740 targeted delivery of the anticancer drug efavirenz to macrophages^[196]. Similarly,
741 Mannosylated fifth-generation Poly(propylene imine) dendrimers (MPPI) were studied as a
742 potential drug carrier for targeted and sustained delivery of the antiretroviral drug lamivudine
743 (3TC) in contrast to plain PPI dendrimers^[32a]. Both PPI and MPPI, when loaded with a drug,
744 were observed to display significant anti-HIV activity compared to the free drug. MPPI showed
745 a substantial increase in the entrapment of the drug over that of PPI. Also, the steric crowding
746 at the periphery in MPPI allowed sustained drug release up to 144 h as compared to 24 h in
747 the case of PPI.

748 **Cancer**

749 Our body undergoes many molecular changes in any disease condition and glycosylation of
750 proteins and lipids is one of these ^[197]. In cancer, atypical glycosylation of affected tissue is
751 often accompanied by the expression of several lectin receptors present on the cell surface
752 displaying an affinity for ligands containing glycan moiety^[33b]. With this in mind, researchers
753 have designed glycoconjugated carriers for targeted delivery and a higher uptake of
754 anticancer drugs into the cancerous tissues and cells^[198].

755 Conjugation of polypropylene imine (PPI) dendrimers with high molecular weight dextran was
756 utilized to prevent the renal elimination of PPI and thus to enhance its retention time in the
757 body^[199]. The formulation not only depicted enhanced permeation and retention (EPR) but
758 also caused an efficient release of the drug in an acidic environment in tumor vessels as
759 compared to normal tissues and this was clearly observed from *in vitro* drug release studies.
760 Similarly, conjugation of galactose to paclitaxel-loaded nanoparticles was seen to help
761 internalization of the particles in the cells via the asialoglycoprotein (ASGP) receptors present
762 on the surface of hepatoma cells^[200]. This interaction can thus be useful in the efficient
763 targeting of hydrophobic anticancer drugs to liver cancer cells.

764 In most advanced cases of gastric cancer, peritoneal dissemination of tumor cells is a common
765 therapeutic problem as it is associated with trans-lymphatic metastasis. Effective inhibition
766 of peritoneal dissemination by Man/CpG DNA lipoplex observed both *in vitro* and *in vivo* was
767 suggested to be obtained by the activation of immunocompetent cells through mannose
768 receptor-mediated CpG DNA transfer^[201]. Additionally, oligomannose-coated liposomes
769 (OMLs) were explored as a delivery system for the anticancer drug and observed to be
770 successfully up taken by mouse peritoneal macrophages and the drug was carried and
771 delivered specifically to metastatic sites in the peritoneal cavity in mice^[202]. The clinical
772 application of the OMLs showed similar results in which the peripheral blood-derived healthy
773 human monocytes/macrophages and the peritoneal washes of patients with gastric cancer
774 took up OMLs^[203]. The results of this study suggest that the OML-based drug delivery system
775 is effective for the targeted delivery of the drug to peritoneal micrometastasis in gastric
776 cancer patients and thus can be evaluated as a platform for novel intraperitoneal
777 chemotherapy with a minimum dose of drug administration.

778 Active targeting of cancer cells for the delivery of cytotoxic agents carried by nanoparticles is
779 enabled by selective overexpression of specific membrane receptors present on the cell
780 surface of cancer cells^[204]. This approach not only increases the specificity of the drug delivery
781 systems towards cancer cells but also maximizes the efficacy of the drug therapeutic by
782 reducing serious side effects associated with the drug by non-specific delivery of the drug^[205].
783 Active targeting of cancer cell-specific receptors results in the drug delivery by endocytosis of
784 the receptor-bound carriers. Following endocytosis, the carrier system is transported from

785 early endosomes to lysosomes where the cytotoxic cargo of the carrier system is finally
786 released.

787 One of the interesting strategies of antitumor therapies that have been explored is the use of
788 lysosomotropic ligand-targeted therapeutics (LTTs) for the delivery of molecules which
789 destabilize lysosomes by induction of lysosomal membrane permeabilization and leakage of
790 hydrolytic enzymes such as cathepsins into the cytoplasm. Cathepsins are lysosomal
791 peptidases belonging to the papain family, which upon re-localization in the cytoplasm, may
792 cause caspase-dependent or independent cell death with or without the involvement of the
793 mitochondria^[206].

794 Mannose-6-phosphate/insulin-like growth factor receptor (M6P/IGF-IIR) participates in the
795 transportation of cellular proteins from the cell surface/trans-Golgi network to lysosomes.
796 The receptor specifically recognizes the mannose-6-phosphate (M6P) carbohydrate moiety
797 and exclusively internalizes systems presenting the M6P group. By taking into consideration
798 the overexpression of IGF-IIR in several human carcinoma cells and its high internalization
799 rate of M6P systems, IGF-IIR has been successfully exploited for the design and development
800 of cancer-targeted drug delivery systems such as M6P functionalized liposomes^[207]. The IGF-
801 IIR expression during fibrosis has also been studied and it was observed that the receptor
802 expression was preferentially higher on fibrogenic cells^[208]. Thus, researchers have used IGF-
803 IIR as a target for the delivery of drugs for liver fibrosis^[208-209].

804 The conjugation of mannose derivative to the solid lipid nanoparticles for the delivery of large
805 doses of anti-cancer drug doxorubicin (DOX) not only minimized the side effects associated
806 with a large dose of the drug and depicted the sustained release nature *in vitro* but also
807 showed an increase in hemocompatibility and biocompatibility of the system *in vivo* which
808 facilitated targeted delivery of the drug to the tumor site^[210].

809 Drug delivery systems play a vital role in enhancing the therapeutic efficacy of cancer
810 treatments by increasing the safety, stability and efficiency of the drug^[211]. However, the drug
811 delivery efficiency remains limited by non-specific targeting of the drug. Among distinct
812 targeting strategies^[211a], most promising is the glycosylation-mediated one^[212]. In
813 comparison to healthy cellular glycosylation, in cancer, tumor cells often express high levels
814 of sialylation, N-linked glycans, truncated glycans and glycosphingolipids^[213]. By taking the

815 aberrant glycosylation in tumor into consideration, various glycan moieties have been
816 attached to the nanocarriers to acquire tumor-targeting abilities^[214] and thus provide new
817 therapeutic opportunities for cancer treatments^[215].

818 **Hepatocellular Carcinoma and Hepatitis**

819 Hepatocytes are liver parenchymal cells that constitute 60-80% of the total mass of the liver
820 tissue. Hepatocytes have unique cell surface receptors called asialoglycoprotein receptors
821 (ASGPr) which can bind specifically to β -D-galactose or N-acetylgalactosamine residues^[216].
822 Carriers modified with these glycan moieties thus have an ability to target hepatocytes via
823 the ASGPr-mediated pathway^[217]. One of the examples of these types of carriers shows that
824 liposomes containing lactobionic acid possess enhanced liver targetability and cause
825 accumulation of the drug in the liver by specifically targeting parenchymal cells expressing
826 ASGPr receptors^[218]. However, to overcome the rapid elimination of the drug-containing
827 liposomes from blood circulation, the liposomes were modified with PEG to create a steric
828 stabilization effect^[219].

829 Glycodendrimers have been introduced as drug carriers in recent years and can be classified
830 as dendrimers with carbohydrate moieties coated, incorporated or attached to a
831 carbohydrate-based, carbohydrate-centered or carbohydrate-coated structure^[220]. The
832 coating of carbohydrates on the dendrimeric system showed a reduction in the hemolytic
833 toxicity associated with the terminal NH₂ groups by neutralizing the charges via conjugation
834 with terminal amine groups^[221].

835 Methotrexate conjugated to the mannosylated human serum albumin (Man-HSA) has been
836 used for specific delivery to liver Kupffer cells thus reaching the liver macrophages in large
837 quantities with an improved pharmacokinetic profile to act on *Leishmania* parasites^[222]. This
838 glycoprotein-based delivery system carries and releases the bioactive compound to the
839 suitable diseased site through a receptor-mediated endocytotic process. Similarly, a liver cell-
840 specific drug delivery system was developed using biotinylated poly(ethylene glycol)
841 conjugated with galactose containing lactobionic acid^[223]. These galactose conjugated
842 nanoparticles when studied as a delivery system for the anti-cancer hydrophobic drugs
843 showed pseudo-zero-order release kinetics over a period of one month.

844 Block copolymers containing carbohydrates have been synthesized via a metal-free
845 organocatalytic ring-opening polymerization (ROP) reaction of functional trimethylene
846 carbonate (TMC) derivatives^[224]. In aqueous solutions, these sugar-functionalized
847 polycarbonate block copolymers can self-assemble into micelles. A study showed that
848 cytotoxicity of doxorubicin (DOX) against HepG2 liver cancer cells significantly increased in
849 galactose-containing micelles over that of glucose-containing micelles and free drug.

850 **Digestive disorders and gastrointestinal diseases**

851 Nanoparticles are often used to increase the bioavailability of orally administered drugs as
852 nanoparticles interact with the gastrointestinal surface by developing adhesive bonds with
853 different components of the mucosa^[225]. The adhesion of nanoparticles to the inner lining of
854 the gut results in localization of delivery of the drug in a specific region of the gut along with
855 an increase in the retention time of the drug in the mucosa^[226]. The adhesion interaction with
856 the mucosa for conventional nanoparticles is non-specific and appears mainly because of the
857 Physico-chemical properties of the drug delivery system^[227]. To overcome this limitation, the
858 delivery systems enriched in mannose are being extensively studied to exploit their high
859 binding affinity to the mannose-binding lectins (MBL) expressed on the lymphoid and non-
860 lymphoid cells of the gut^[228]. Although the conjugation of Acyclovir (ACV)- entrapped
861 liposomes (ACV-lip) with mannose did not result in an increase in entrapment efficiency and
862 loading efficiency of the system, it nevertheless enhanced the bioavailability of the poorly
863 absorbable drug significantly when studied *in vitro*^[229]. This result accords with the hypothesis
864 of the interaction of the mannose containing system with MBLs expressed by gut cells which
865 could promote substantial drug transport through the gi-tract. In a similar study,
866 mannosylated nanoparticles showed a strong capacity to adhere to the outer layer of the
867 ileum (mucus layer) region of the small intestine and penetrate the Peyer's patches^[226]. The
868 strong bioadhesive capacity and tissue affinity to gut-associated lymphoid tissue of
869 mannosylated nanoparticles after their oral administration suggests that these particles can
870 be used as a promising vehicle for oral drug delivery. In addition, non-peptidic ligands and
871 glycan moieties attached to nanoparticles for targeted delivery to M cells have shown
872 promising results as delivery systems for oral immunization^[230].

Table 4: Summary of therapeutic applications of glycoconjugates

Targeted disease	Type of carrier	Conjugate sugar	Carrier compound	Active compound/ drug	Targeted moiety/ cells	In vitro model	In vivo model	Rote of administrati on	Effect of glycosylation/ Application	Ref.
HIV	Liposomes	Galactose	Egg PC: CH: PE in different molar ratios	Azidothymidine	Monocytes/ macrophages	-	Male albino rats (SD strain) (100 ± 20 g)	Intravenous injection	Enhanced cellular uptake, sustained drug release, high distribution of drug and reduction in side-effects associated with the drug	[193]
	Liposomes	Galactose Fucose Mannose	Lipid mixture of egg PC, CH, DMPE (Gal-DMPE) in molar ratio 7:2:1	Stavudine	Macrophages and Hepatocytes	-	Male albino rats (SD stain) (100 ± 20 g)	Intravenous injection	Enhanced entrapment efficiency, smaller particle size, sustained release of drug, decrease in surface charge of liposomes, localized delivery of the drug.	[194]
	Liposomes	Galactose	Lipid mixture of egg PC, CH, DMPE (Gal-DMPE) in molar ratio 7:2:1	Radio-labeled stavudine	Macrophages	HIV-1 Infected MT2 cell line	Strain A mice (25-30 g) (8-12 weeks old)	Intravenous injection	Increase in accumulation of liposomes in the liver, decrease in bone-marrow cytotoxicity of the drug	[195]
	Liposomes	Mannose	Man-4-Chol/DOPE (6:4), DC-Chol/DOPE (6:4), DOTMA/DOPE (1:1), Man-4-Chol/DC-Chol/DOPE (3:3:4)	Plasmid DNA encoding luciferase gene (pCMV-Luc)	Macrophages	Mice macrophages	ICR mice (5 weeks old)	Intravenous injection	Selective delivery of plasmid DNA to the liver, higher transfection activity, applicability of the system for targeted delivery to splenic macrophages, highly efficient non-viral gene transfer both in vivo and in vitro via recognition by mannose receptors	[161b]
	Dendrimer s	Mannose	Fifth-generation poly(propylene imine) dendrimers	Lamivudine (3TC)	Macrophages	MT2 cell line	-	-	Improved safety and efficacy of the drug, a significant increase in entrapment efficiency, sustained drug release, significant increase in cellular uptake	[32a]
	Dendrimer s	Mannose	Poly(propylene imine) dendrimer	Efavirenz	Monocytes/ macrophages	Hepatoma (Hep G2) cell line	-	-	Negligible cytotoxicity, high drug entrapment efficiency, scanty hemotoxicity and a significant increase in cellular uptake	[196]

Targeted disease	Type of carrier	Conjugate sugar	Carrier compound	Active compound/ drug	Targeted moiety/ cells	In vitro model	In vivo model	Rote of administrati on	Effect of glycosylation/ Application	Ref.
Cancer	Liposomes	Mannose-6-phosphate	DPPC and CH (50:50), DPPC: CH: Chol-M6P (50:30:20)	C6-Ceramide	Tumor cells	HDF and MCF7 cells	-	-	Selective induction of apoptosis in cancer cells	[207d]
	Liposomes	Mannose	-	Plasmid DNA	Dendritic cells	Primary mbmDCs from C57Bl/6J mice	C57Bl/6J mice	Subcutaneous injection	A promising application for direct <i>in vivo</i> targeting to DCs. Observed long-lasting antitumor response and significant memory response	[231]
	Liposome	Mannose	L- α -Phosphatidylcholine, cholesterol	⁶⁴ Cu	Tumor-associated macrophages	Murine bone marrow-derived macrophages	Female FVB mice (6-8 weeks old)	Intravenous injection	Confirmation of the role of M2 subtype of macrophages in cancer progression, targeted delivery of radioactive agents	[187]
	Liposomes	D-Mannose	2X3- DOPE	Plasmid DNA and RNA	Dendritic cells	DC progenitor cells, immature DC cells obtained from the bone marrow of C57Bl/6J mice	Male C57Bl/6J mice (10-14 weeks old)	Intravenous injection	Efficient and targeted delivery of pDNA and RNA observed in vitro, the ability to deliver RNA in vivo with the induction of antitumor response	[232]
	Liposomes	Mannose	Man/CpG DNA lipoplex	CpG DNA	Peritoneal macrophages	Mouse peritoneal macrophages	Male Balb/c mice (4 weeks old)	Intraperitoneal administration	The increased survival rate of mice treated with mannosylated lipoplex, efficient immunotherapy Inhibition of tumor cells proliferation in the greater omentum and the mesentery.	[201]
	Liposomes	Fucose	DPPC, Chol, ganglioside, DCP, DPPE mixed in different molar ratios	Cisplatin	Pancreatic cancer cells	BxPC-3 cell line	Nude mice (4-6 weeks old)	Intravenous injection	Targeted delivery of the drug, effective inhibition of CA19-9 producing cancer cells in vitro and tumor growth in vivo	[233]

Targeted disease	Type of carrier	Conjugate sugar	Carrier compound	Active compound/ drug	Targeted moiety/ cells	In vitro model	In vivo model	Rote of administrati on	Effect of glycosylation/ Application	Ref.
	Nanoparti cles	Mannan	Poly (ε-caprolactone)-PEG-poly(ε-caprolactone) (PCEC) polymer	Human basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF)	Dendritic cells	-	Female C57BL/6 mice (5 weeks old)	Subcutaneo us injection)	Improved humoral immunity due to targeted delivery to dendritic cells.	[234]
	Nanoparti cles	Mannose	Chitosan	Plasmid DNA encoding murine IL-12	Dendritic cells	NCTC 3749 cell line	BALB/c mice (6-8 weeks old)	Injected in the tumor	Small size of mannosylated particles, low cytotoxicity, sustained gene expression.	[235]
	Nanoparti cles	Analogue of Mannose-6-Phosphat e (M6C)	Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN)	One- and two-photon photosensiti zers	Prostate cancer cells	LNCaP cell line	-	-	Efficient targeting, imaging and photodynamic therapy	[207b]
	Polymer conjugate	Mannan	Methotrexate (MTX)	Methotrexa te	Lung	A549 cell line, B16 cell line	Female and Male (BALB/c X DBA/2)F1 (CD ₂ F ₁) mice (12- 24 weeks old)	Intraperiton eal administrati on	Improved antitumor activity compare to free methotrexate with intraperitoneal administration of the drug, potential application for the treatment of advanced ovarian cancer.	[236]
	Polymer conjugate	Fucose	pLK-Fucose	Phosphorot hioate oligonucleot ide	Lung	A549 cell line	-	-	Reduction in toxicity of carrier system, selective inhibition of gene expression, increase in uptake	[237]
	Human serum albumin	Mannose-6-Phosphat e	HSA-M6P	Doxorubicin	Subcutaneous tissue	B16-F10 cell line, C26 cell line	Male C57BL/6 and Balb/c mice (20-25 g)	Intravenous injection	Targeted therapy of tumors through IGF-IIR receptors was achieved, high cellular uptake, increase in internalization and enhanced efficacy of the drug	[207a]
Hepatocel lular carcinoma (HCC)	Liposomes	Lactobioni c acid	Lipid mixture of HSPC: CH: CHS-ED-LA (60:40:0/10)	Doxorubicin	Liver	-	Female KM mice (18-22 g)	Intravenous injection	Enhanced liver targetability and accumulation of liposomes in liver	[218]

Targeted disease	Type of carrier	Conjugate sugar	Carrier compound	Active compound/ drug	Targeted moiety/ cells	In vitro model	In vivo model	Rote of administrati on	Effect of glycosylation/ Application	Ref.
	Liposomes	Lactobionic acid	Lipid mixture of HSPC:CH: PEG ₂₀₀₀ -CHEMS (60:40:2), HSPC: CH: CHS-ED-LA: PEG ₂₀₀₀ -CHEMS (60:30:10:2)	Doxorubicin	Liver	-	Female KM mice (18 – 22 g)	Intravenous injection	Controlled drug delivery to hepatocytes, Efficient liver targetability, enhanced accumulation of the drug in liver, enhanced therapeutic benefits such as the decrease in liver damage and enhanced therapeutic efficiency	[219]
	Nanoparticles	Galactose	Bovine serum albumin (BSA)	Oridonin	Hepatocytes	-	-	-	Sustained-release profile in vitro, crosslinking degree influences the rate of release	[238]
	Nanoparticles	Galactose	PBLG/PEG	Paclitaxel	Hepatocytes	P388 cell line, SK-Hep01 cell line, HepG2 cell line	-	-	Selective delivery of the drug to HepG2 cells via ASGP receptors.	[239]
Liver fibrosis	Polymeric micelle	Mannose-6-Phosphate	GDC-0449	PEG-PCD	Liver	-	C57BL/6 male mice (10-12 weeks old)	Intravenous injection	Increased retention and accumulation of drug in the target site (Liver)	[209]
	Human serum albumin	Mannose-6-Phosphate	M6PHSA	Doxorubicin	Hepatic stellate cells (HSC)	HSC isolate from male Wistar rats (>400 g)	Male Wistar rats (220-240 g)	Intravenous injection	Significant inhibition of HSC proliferation in vitro, successful delivery to HSCs in vivo	[240]
	Human serum albumin	Mannose-6-Phosphate	HSA-M6P	Mycophenolic acid (MPA)	Liver	3T3 fibroblasts cell line	Male wistar rats (220-240 g)	Intravenous injection	IGF-IIR receptor upregulated in fibroblast-like cells in fibrotic liver, selective drug delivery at early stage of fibrotic diseases	[208]
Hepatitis B	Microcapsules	Galactose	Poly(vinyl galactose ester-co-methacryloxyethyl trimethylammonium)	Acyclovir	Hepatocytes	-	-	-	Sustained drug release, promising system to encapsulate and deliver various therapeutic agents to hepatic cells.	[241]

Targeted disease	Type of carrier	Conjugate sugar	Carrier compound	Active compound/ drug	Targeted moiety/ cells	In vitro model	In vivo model	Rote of administrati on	Effect of glycosylation/ Application	Ref.
	Vesicles – nonionic surfactant based vesicles (niosomes)	Mannan	um chloride) (PGEDMC) / poly(styrenesulfonate) (PSS) Span 60: Ch: stearylamine in molar ratios 6: 3: 1	Plasmid DNA	Gut associated lymphoid tissue (GALT) Dendritic cells	-	BALB/c mice (4-8 week old)	Oral administration	Stabilization of vesicles in GI environment, safe, economic and stable system with potential for application in oral delivery of vaccines	[242]
Malaria	Dendrimer s	Galactose	Fourth generation poly-L-lysine dendrimer	Chloroquine phosphate	macrophages	-	Male albino rats (SD strain) (130 ± 10 g)	Intravenous injection	Reduction in hemolytic toxicity of poly-L-dendrimers.	[221]
Tuberculosis	Dendrimer s	Mannose	5G EDA PPI dendrimer	Rifampicin	Alveolar macrophages	Vero cells (ATCC-CCL -81)	-	-	Biocompatible system with site-specific delivery and enhanced cellular uptake.	[243]
Pulmonary diseases	Liposomes	Mannose	DSPC, CH, F-DHPE and Man-C4-Chol in different molar ratios	-	Alveolar macrophages	Primary culture rat alveolar macrophages	Male wistar rats (250 – 300 g) (8 weeks old)	Intratracheal administration	Efficient and selective targeting to alveolar macrophages, high cellular uptake with increase in mannose content	[244]
Rheumatoid arthritis	Liposomes	Mannose	AChx/DC-Chol/DOPE	Plasmid DNA expressing human IL-10	Tumor-associated macrophages	-	-	-	Successfully synthesized neoglycolipids, high mannose type neoglycolipids actively targeted macrophages	[245]
AM-associated diseases	Liposomes	Mannose	HSPC, CH, DCP and Mannose in different molar ratios	-	Alveolar macrophages	SD rat alveolar macrophages	Male SD rats (190-220 g)	Sprayed into the lungs with liquid MicroSprayer™	Higher cellular uptake of mannosylated liposomes by NR8383, efficient and targeted aerosolized delivery to alveolar macrophage	[246]
-	Liposomes	Mannose	Egg PC: M ₃ -DPPE/M ₁ -DPPE in	Protein	Dendritic cells	Human MoDCs, murine	-	-	Increase in uptake for tri-mannose derivatives, increase in proliferation	[247]

Targeted disease	Type of carrier	Conjugate sugar	Carrier compound	Active compound/ drug	Targeted moiety/ cells	In vitro model	In vivo model	Rote of administrati on	Effect of glycosylation/ Application	Ref.
-	Liposomes	Galactose	two different molar ratios Lipid mixture of soybean phosphatidylcholine (SPC) : Cholesterol : NGPE in molar ratios of 55 : 44: 11.2	-	Liver – Parenchymal cells, Hepatocytes	bone-marrow derived DCs	Male swiss albino mice (28 – 30 g)	Intravenous injection	of primed T cells in vitro, no increase in dendritic cell activation Significant increase in uptake in liver, decrease in uptake of drug in spleen, specific binding to parenchymal cells. The system effective for delivery of drugs, enzymes, genetic materials, anti-sense oligonucleotides selectively to liver parenchymal cells.	[248]
-	Liposomes	Mannose	Lipid mixture of soybean phosphatidylcholine (SPC): Cholesterol: NGPE in molar ratios of 55:44: 11.2	-	Liver – Parenchymal cells, Hepatocytes	-	Male swiss albino mice (28 – 30 g)	Intravenous injection	Significant increase in uptake in liver, decrease in uptake of drug in spleen, specific binding to parenchymal cells. The system effective for selective delivery of therapeutic agents to liver parenchymal cells.	[248]
-	Superpara magnetic nanoparticles	Galactose	Fe ₃ O ₄	-	Hepatocytes	HepG2 cell line	-	-	Low toxicity, high cellular uptake.	[249]
-	Nanoparticles	Galactose	Polyphosphoramidate (PPA)	DNA	Hepatocyte	HeLa cell line, HepG2 cell line, Primary rat hepatocytes	-	-	Lower DNA compaction capacity with increase in galactose substitution, significantly higher gene transfection efficiency observed for ternary nanoparticles and reduction in cytotoxicity was observed with increase in galactose substitution of nanoparticles.	[250]

873 **Concluding remarks and future perspectives**

874 Glycosylation is emerging as a versatile technique for achieving effective therapy and
875 diagnosis as a result of the distinctive recognition between the sugar molecules and the
876 respective receptors. The knowledge of various lectin receptors present in our body, the
877 cells/tissues they are expressed on and the glycans that can be recognized by them along with
878 different glycosylation strategies that can be employed to achieve the desired
879 glycoconjugation of the materials in focus is essential for the design of efficient
880 glycotherapeutics. Recent advances in glycotherapeutics show that the researchers have
881 exploited this knowledge for the design of various glycan-based drug molecules and drug
882 delivery systems. However, lectins have mostly been used as target moieties in this process.
883 There is a huge area of research yet to be explored by reversing the role of glycans and lectins
884 and using glycan moieties in our body as potential targets.

885 It is important to understand that the recognition of multiple glycan moieties by targeted
886 receptors is an important issue associated with glycan – lectin interaction at the moment and
887 one that could significantly affect the targeting efficiency of the system. For example, a
888 serum-type mannan-binding protein, a specific lectin for the innate immune system, could
889 also recognize D-mannose, L-fucose, and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine^[251]. This limitation could
890 significantly reduce the therapeutic efficiency of the delivery system and may also cause
891 undesirable effects of the carrier drug *in vivo*. Thus, glycan-lectin interaction needs to be
892 explored in further detail. It will be useful if research is done to understand the changes
893 incurred in the interactions based on the location of the receptors in the body to engineer the
894 materials to obtain site-tailored interaction. This will greatly improve the specificity of the
895 glycoconjugated delivery systems and thus the therapeutic efficiency of the drug along with
896 a decrease in the side effects associated with non-specific targeting.

897 The reason carbohydrates are being acknowledged as a promising tool for forming targeted
898 delivery systems is because of their multiple hydroxyl groups and the ability to be modified in
899 a facile manner. However, several issues need to be addressed for the design of glycosylated
900 delivery systems for practical applications. One such issue is the bioconjugation of delivery
901 systems by glycosylation. This may result in a variation in physicochemical properties of
902 delivery vehicles such as size distribution, surface charge, and biocompatibility as well^[252].
903 Although studies have shown that glycoconjugation has improved the targetability of the

904 delivery systems, the effect on encapsulation efficiency, size and thus the application has not
905 been correlated. Also, the interaction of glycosylated nanocarriers with other cells, tissues
906 and organs beyond those targeted impose a limitation on the system. Recent studies have
907 shown that the glycosylation might affect other organs by off-target effect, however, further
908 investigation is still required^[253].

909 The clinical application of glycosylated strategies is challenging because of the safety and
910 reproducibility concerns^[213a]. Recent studies have shown that the combination of
911 glycosylation strategies and immunological therapy demonstrates a potential for cancer
912 therapy^[254]. The strategy can be exploited to enhance the properties and the clinical
913 applicability of the glycosylated systems for various applications including cancer.

914 In summary, we have reviewed different strategies that can be used for functionalising
915 glycans to materials, a variety of lectin receptors and their role in glycotherapy, and the
916 therapeutic applications of different glycoconjugates that have been synthesized over the last
917 few decades. Although the research in glycotherapeutics has exponentially increased in last
918 few years and novel and efficient systems for exploiting the understanding of glycan-lectin
919 interactions have been developed to achieve the ultimate goal of clinical translation, further
920 innovations are crucial in the field of discovery of more-specific receptors as well as in their
921 carbohydrate ligands and the development of practical fabrication methods for glycosylated
922 drugs and delivery systems.

923

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